

ROBUST ESTIMATION OF AN AR MULTI-CHANNEL MODEL BY USING t -DISTRIBUTION ASSUMPTION

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a new error criteria for determining the optimal multi-channel model system. The error criteria is based on assuming that the probability density function of the resulted error signal is t -distributed with α degrees of freedom. A small weighting factor is assigned for large amplitude signal portion parts and large weighting factor is used for small amplitude signal portion sections. By doing so, the effect of large amplitude signal portions to the estimated system parameter is reduced. The simulation results show that the average of the obtained parameter by using small degree of freedom α t -distribution assumption is closer to the ideal parameter than that when the conventional Gaussian assumption is applied. Furthermore, the standard deviation of the estimation result by applying small α t assumption is smaller than that when $\alpha = \infty$ is utilized.

1 INTRODUCTION

There are many applications of multi-channel systems, such as in radar, multi-sensor, image analysis etc. In many of those applications, it is desired to determine the optimal model. Least square (L_2) method is widely used in estimating optimal model and also for multi-channel cases [1]. In the least square method all signal portions are assigned the same weighting factor. Large portion of signals with small amplitude have less influence than that of small portion of signals with large amplitude [2].

It has been a common knowledge nowadays that practically we encounter non Gaussian signals. The probability density function (PDF) of some parts of the those signals is not Gaussian. Those signals have more large amplitude signal portions than that of the Gaussian signal. Because of that, small portions of signal with large amplitude have more effect to the obtained AR model than that of large portions of the signal with small amplitude [2]. In this case, the performance of the L_2 method dramatically deteriorate. It is necessary that the effect of large amplitude signal is suppressed to get more accurate estimate.

In the past, there have been many efforts done to

reduce this effect in one channel case [2], [4], [3]. The Huber's uncommon distribution is applied in [2] and [4]. On the other hand [3] use the t distribution assumption for reducing the effect of the large amplitude signal.

It has been proved that the performance of the t -distribution assumption surpass the one of Huber's distribution. The accuracy of the estimation results is better. The standard deviation by using the t -distribution assumption is smaller than that of Huber's show that t -distribution is more success in suppressing the effect of large amplitude signal than that of Huber's. Because of that, in this paper, we propose an expansion of the previous method in [3] into multi-channel case. The objective of the proposed method is to provide a method to obtained accurate estimation for multi-channel estimation case.

2 THE PROPOSED IDEA

We consider a K channel one dimensional signals $x_k(n)$, $0 \leq k \leq (K-1)$, which are assumed to be generated by exciting a K channel AR model by a certain K channel random noise $\epsilon_k(n)$, $1 \leq k \leq K$. It is assumed that the excitation $\epsilon_k(n)$ for $1 \leq k \leq K$ are all-independent each other. An event in one channel is completely independent from another an event on the other channels. Furthermore, it is assumed that sample of the excitation on a certain channel is identically and independently distributed. The mathematical relation between the excitation signal $\epsilon_k(n)$ and the the considered signals $x_k(n)$, both on a certain channel k is expressed as

$$x_k(n) = \epsilon_n(k) - \sum_{j=1}^J a_k(j)x_k(n-j). \quad (1)$$

The order of the AR model is denoted as J . The optimal parameter $a_k(j)$, $0 \leq k \leq (K-1)$ and $1 \leq j \leq J$ have to be estimated by minimizing an objective function

$$\xi(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(\epsilon_k(n)). \quad (2)$$

Theoretically, the length of the analysis window $N = \infty$. Practically it is not possible to wait until all data are

available before calculating the optimal model. Therefore, $0 \leq N$ is selected to be long enough to get a good estimation. On the other hand, to avoid non-stationarity, N should not be too long. In this paper, we select $N = 200 \sim 300$ samples.

The objective function is selected based on a certain assumption about the excitation. In this paper, the objective function is derived by assuming that the excitation signal has a certain probability density function (PDF). The selection of $f(x)$ is crucial. Since the objective function will directly determine the quality of the estimate parameter, we have to carefully select $f(x)$. The Gaussian PDF is commonly used for $f(x)$. In this approach all signals are assigned the same weighting function, so that small portions of residual signals with large amplitude has more effect to the obtained optimal parameter than that of portions of residual signals with small amplitude. Recently, it has been proved we can obtain good estimation with this assumption only when the excitation signal is really Gaussian. Whenever some parts of the excitation deviate from Gaussian distribution, the quality of the obtained estimate rapidly deteriorate [3]. The standard deviation (SD) of the obtained estimation result is large and it is very much affected by the position of the analysis window. The result is very much affected by large amplitude signal samples.

The quality of the estimation by pretending Gaussian assumption can be achieved by applying a nonlinear function to the analyzed data. The nonlinear weighting function has to carefully adjusted, so that all parts of the data that are used for calculating the optimal model are Gaussian. The large amplitude signal samples have to be suppress. Since practically, we have no a-priori knowledge about the PDF of the excitation signal, it is very difficult to determine the optimal weighting function.

Another approach can also be applied by carefully select the assumed PDF, so that the effect of the large amplitude signal samples is reduced. The appropriate PDF for accomplishing the purpose is the heavy-tailed type. The probability on the tail of the heavy-tailed PDF is higher than that of Gaussian. It has been recently proposed the usage of heavy-tailed t distribution to improve the estimation quality. Since it has been proved that we can better quality by applying t assumption than that of Gaussian and 2-tailed Huber's distribution, in this paper we propose the usage of t distribution with α degrees of freedom to increase the quality of the multi-channel parameter estimate. The PDF of the t -distributed data x is [5]

$$g_\alpha(x) = K_\alpha \{w_\alpha(x)\}^{\frac{\alpha+1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: The graphic of $\beta_\alpha(x)$ with various degree of freedom α .

where

$$K_\alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha\pi}} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha+1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}, \quad \text{and} \quad w_\alpha(y) = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{y^2}{\alpha}\right)}. \quad (4)$$

Gaussian distribution is one special case of t distribution; i.e. when $\alpha = \infty$. Thus, the proposed method in this paper can be seen as a generalization of the conventional multi-channel parameter estimation approach that use Gaussian assumption.

Assuming that all samples are independent, the optimal solution is solved by using the maximum likelihood method. The log likelihood of all signal samples over all channel $1 \leq k \leq K$ and within analysis window $0 \leq n \leq (N-1)$ is

$$L(\mathbf{A}|\epsilon_k(n)) = \log K_\alpha - \hat{L}(\mathbf{A}) \quad (5)$$

where

$$\hat{L}(\mathbf{A}) = \frac{\alpha+1}{2} \sum_{k=x+10}^K \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \left\{ \log \left(w_\alpha \left(\frac{\epsilon_k(n)}{\hat{s}} \right) \right) \right\} \quad (6)$$

The desired coefficient matrix is arranged in a matrix

$$\mathbf{A}(m,n) = [\mathbf{a}(0) \quad \mathbf{a}(1) \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{a}(I)]^T \quad (7)$$

where

$$\mathbf{a}(p) = [a(p,0) \quad a(p,1) \quad \cdots \quad a(p,J)]. \quad (8)$$

Since the degree of freedom α is a pre-selected value, the first term in (5) is a constant. Thus, maximizing the log likelihood function in (5) is solved by minimizing (6).

When the optimal solution is obtained, the first order derivative

$$\nabla = \beta_\alpha(\epsilon_k(n)) \mathbf{x}_k(n) = 0. \quad (9)$$

The influence function is defined as

$$\beta_\alpha \left(\frac{\epsilon_k(n)}{\hat{s}} \right) = \frac{\epsilon_k(n)}{\hat{s}} w_\alpha \left(\frac{\epsilon_k(n)}{\hat{s}} \right) \quad (10)$$

and

$$\mathbf{x}_l(i) = [x_l(i-1) \quad a_l(i-2) \quad \cdots \quad a_l(i-p)]^T. \quad (11)$$

The vector $\mathbf{x}_k(n)$ in (9) depend on the analysis input signal. Thus, the weighting function $\beta_\alpha(\epsilon_k(n))$ (9) has a very important role in determining the optimal solution. The plot of $\beta_\alpha(x)$ for various degree of freedom α is depicted in Fig. 1. The curve in Fig. 1 for $\alpha = \infty$ shows that an equal weighting function is assigned for both small and large $\epsilon_k(n)$. Large amplitude $\epsilon_k(n)$ has large influence to the obtained optimal solution. The obtained estimate varies depending on the analysis window position. This is the case when the conventional multi-channel parameter estimate method is used. On the other hand, when $\alpha = 3$ is utilized, a small weighting function is applied for large $\epsilon_k(n)$. Large weighting function is used for small $\epsilon_k(n)$. In this case, the influence of large amplitude $\epsilon_k(n)$ to the optimal solution is reduced. It is expected that the estimation results is less affected by the analysis window position. We expect to get more precise and smaller SD results than that when $\alpha = \infty$ is used.

Since the relation between $\hat{L}(\mathbf{A})$ and the desired vector parameter $\mathbf{A}$ is nonlinear, the optimal solution is solved by using the Newton Raphson nonlinear optimization approach [6]. The optimal solution is calculated iteratively by

$$\mathbf{A}^q(n) = \mathbf{A}^{q-1}(n) - \mathbf{H}^q(n) \nabla^q(n) \quad (12)$$

where q denoted the iteration step and $\mathbf{H}^q(n)$ is the inverse of the Hessian matrix.

Instead of using the exact second order derivative matrix or Hessian matrix

$$\mathbf{P}^q(n) = \frac{\partial^2 \hat{L}(\mathbf{A})}{\partial \mathbf{A} \partial \mathbf{A}^T} \quad (13)$$

that can not be guaranteed to be positive definite, in the iteration we use a $((J.K) * (J.K)) \mathbf{G}^q(n)$ matrix in (14) as an approximation.

We define

$$H(s, u, r, t) = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_s(n-u) x_r(n-t) w_\alpha \left(\frac{\epsilon_k(n)}{\hat{s}} \right). \quad (15)$$

The gradient vector $\nabla^q(n)$ is given in (9).

To get a scale invariant estimate, a robust scale $\hat{s}$ estimate is used. The scale estimate is calculated by using the MAD [5]

$$\hat{s} = \text{median}|\gamma(i)| \quad (16)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq I$. Large I will produce accurate estimate. On the other hand larger I will cost more calculation to solve $\hat{s}$. Compromising those two factors, in this paper we select $I = 100$. $\gamma(i)$ is obtained from the residual $\epsilon_k(n)$. When there are K channel, then we take $100/K$ residual from each channel to form $\gamma(i)$.

The recursion is terminated whenever either

$$|L^q(n) - L^{q-1}(n)| \leq 0.01 \quad (17)$$

or

$$\sqrt{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{\partial L}{\partial a_k(j)}} \leq 0.01 \quad (18)$$

is satisfied.

The simulation results show that by using the iteration strategy in (12) and small α , we can get better estimation result than that when $\alpha = \infty$ or Gaussian assumption is applied. The result is closer to the ideal value and the standard deviation of the estimation is smaller.

3 THE SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed algorithm has been applied to estimate the parameter of a synthetic multi-channel signal. The synthetic signal was generated by exciting a 4-channel 10-th order AR model by a random binary signal. The parameters of the AR systems are chosen from analyzing 4 segments of a real human speech. The length of each segment is 256 msec and it is arbitrary chosen among an utterance $/a/$. The random binary signal $b(n)$ was generated using

$$b(n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{when } g(n) \geq 0.75 \\ -1 & \text{when } g(n) \leq -0.75 \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where $g(n)$ is a random signal that is flatly distributed between -1 and 1 .

We estimate the parameter of the system from the synthetic signal only. No further information is supplied to the estimator. We use the estimation strategy as explained in (12). The length of the analysis frame is set to be 256 samples for each channel. The sum of the square of the error between the estimated and the actual parameters of the system

$$E = \frac{1}{J.K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^J (a(k, j) - \hat{a}(k, j))^2 \quad (20)$$

was calculated. We did the same calculation for 200 different consecutive frames. We applied 200 different positions for those 200 frames are different. The average(AV) and the standard deviation(SD) of the error E were determined from those 200 frames and plotted as a function of degree of freedom α . The plots are depicted in Fig. 3

$$\mathbf{G}^q(n) = \begin{bmatrix} G(1, 1, 1, 1) & G(1, 1, 1, 2) & \cdots & G(1, 1, 1, p) & G(1, 1, 2, 1) & \cdots & GH(1, 1, K, J) \\ G(1, 2, 1, 1) & G(1, 2, 1, 2) & \cdots & G(1, 2, 1, p) & G(1, 2, 2, 1) & \cdots & H(1, 2, K, J) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ G(1, p, 1, 1) & G(1, p, 1, 2) & \cdots & G(1, p, 1, p) & G(1, p, 2, 1) & \cdots & G(1, p, K, J) \\ G(2, 1, 1, 1) & G(2, 1, 1, 2) & \cdots & G(2, 1, 1, p) & G(2, 1, 2, 1) & \cdots & G(2, 1, K, J) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ G(K, J, 1, 1) & G(K, J, 1, 2) & \cdots & G(K, J, 1, p) & G(K, J, 2, 1) & \cdots & G(K, J, K, J) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Figure 2: The AV and the SD of E for various degree of freedom α with random binary excitation.

Figure 3: The AV and SD of E for various degree of freedom α with Gaussian excitation.

The plot in Fig. 3 show that by applying small α assumption, the average of E is smaller than that when large α is used. Thus it can be concluded that by using small α assumption, we can obtain more precise estimation. The estimate parameter is closer to the true parameter than that for large α . Furthermore, the plot in Fig. 3 also show that by using small α , the standard deviation (SD) is also smaller than that of large α . This fact shows that the variation of the obtained estimate by using small α is less than that of large α . Since in this simulation we apply an impulsive signal, it can be concluded that the effect of large amplitude signal can be suppressed by utilizing small α .

The result of the simulation for Gaussian excitation in Fig 3 shows the same behavior. The performance of the estimator with small α is always better than the conventional Gaussian approach. In the real application, we have no apriori information about the probability behavior of the excitation. Therefore, finally we recommend the usage of t -distribution with small α assumption for multi-channel estimation problem.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed a new robust estimation method for an AR multi-channel by using a t -distribution assumption. Whenever the considered signal is impulsive, we

can get more accurate and more efficient estimate by applying small α assumption. Further applications of the proposed method and the method to overcome the calculation complexity due to iteration are still studind and will reported somewhere else.

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